

Safety Status of Secondary Schools Buildings for Reducing Fire Incidents in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: School buildings are essential for teaching and learning hence the safety of users of these buildings during fire emergency needs to be ensured. Thus this study assessed safety status of buildings in public and private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis. It focuses on determining classrooms, laboratories, computer/store rooms, and staff rooms' safety and giving recommendation on safety in schools. Descriptive survey approach was used. The target population was 18 public and private secondary schools. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to obtain sample size of 700 respondents consisting 143 teachers and 557 students from the sampled schools. Data were collected through questionnaire administration, and participatory observation. Analysis was facilitated via the evaluation of Kendall's coefficient of concordance (w), that is, the degree of agreement amongst the respondents. The results revealed that Kwara State Fire Service Headquarters, Ilorin does not carry out regular inspection of schools' buildings for fire safety compliance. Students (72.22%) in most secondary schools learn in unsafe classrooms and laboratories due to grilled windows, and doors in some cases. Kendall's analysis shows a low (0.454) degree of agreement amongst respondents on the safety status of school buildings. It was concluded that public and private secondary school buildings in Ilorin metropolis are not safe for teaching and learning in the face of fire emergency. Key recommendations are that windows of laboratories, classrooms and staffroom(s) should not be grilled and doors should be outwardly opening for safety of students and their educators against stampeding during fire tragedy.

Keywords: Fire, Incident, Safety, Secondary Schools, Ilorin Metropolis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Secondary school enrolment in Nigeria is on the increase, hence buildings are provided without sufficient consideration for safety of the buildings used for teaching-learning process. School buildings are crucial resources for education since the latter enhances all-round development of a man and his environment (Lu, 2004). School buildings are essential for effective teaching and learning process. They play pivotal roles in the actualization of educational goals and objectives when safety of staff and students are guaranteed (Squelch, 2001). Fire incident when it occurs in school threatens lives and

properties of students, teachers, and supporting staff.

Without doubt, fire is a most disaster that building and its occupants face (Tom, 2015). Hence, safety of learners and their instructors in (public and private) secondary schools must be a top priority (Awodiji, Ogbudinkpa, and Osasuyin, 2015). In an attempt to ensure the safety of users of school buildings (such as students, teachers, supporting staff, and visitors among others), and for school to be recognized as safe and prepared for fire incident, different safety laws, guidelines and recommendations have been made at country and globe levels. For safety of schools, Government of Kenya

{GoK}, (2008) enacted that, windows and doors in school buildings must not be grilled (affixed with burglary proof) and should be easy to open outwards. GoK (2008) furthered that, dormitories should have a door at each end and an additional emergency exit at the middle with a clear label of 'Emergency Exit'. The emergency exit must not be obstructed, and should swing in the direction of exit traffic flow. Ongori (2014) also submitted that a guideline for fire prevention in secondary school buildings also mandate firefighting equipment to be functioning and placed at easily accessible points. Combustible materials must not be used for decorations or in building components (GoK, 2008).

International Financial Corporation {IFC}, (2010) and Nyagawa (2017) recommended that, all classroom doors, doors of high-occupancy rooms, and doors to entrances must be outwardly open, emergency exit pathways must be kept clear from obstruction, and wherever possible classrooms should have two exits and dormitories should not be overcrowded. Moreover, fire suppression equipment should be located appropriately and maintained in good working condition, flammable and combustible materials such as paper are limited, isolated, eliminated and separated away from dangerous interactions and heat sources. Nyagawa (2017) also reported that the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training (MoEVT) of Tanzania in one of its circular mandates school administrators to ensure availability of regular inspection, servicing and testing of fire extinguishers and smoke detectors among others.

Like other countries, Federal Republic of Nigeria prescribed some guidelines and requirements for all buildings including school buildings in the country. Among these, the National Building Code {NBC}, (2006) of Nigeria precisely Section 7.1.4 prescribed the requirements for buildings used for educational purposes (Group C occupancies). Section 7.2.1.7 of NBC maintained that "all buildings

(including secondary schools buildings) and structures involved in the use and handling of flammable or explosive materials and other hazardous substances shall be inspected for fire safety compliance in accordance with the National Fire Safety Code". Section 7.2.1.8 maintained that the inspection team shall include the Code Enforcement Officer, Fire Safety Officer, Health Officer, and other agencies charged with the responsibilities. Similarly, Fire Service Act, Cap F29, laws of the Federation of Nigeria under National Fire Safety Code (2013) empowers and mandates fire service headquarters to inspect school building and its structural plan before construction and after establishment to ascertain fire safety compliance (Kwara State Fire Service Headquarters KSFSH, 2017).

Despite the different safety guidelines set for the safety of school and its users, issues of school infrastructure (school buildings) safety remains a challenge (UNICEF, 2009). Lending credence to this view, Makachia, Gatebe and Makhonge (2014), and Sankey, Joshua and Omole (2014) described poor conditions of school facilities and lack of fire safety anticipation as some of the factors perpetuating high risks of fire in school buildings. Kihila (2017) positioned that lack of enforcement and poor implementation of building codes and safety guidelines are some of the problems facing school buildings in cities of developing countries.

Some works have investigated the issue of fire safety in educational institutions, and a few of them are examined to establish the rationale for this present study in Kwara State. Akumu (2013) examined the disaster awareness and preparedness of secondary schools in Homa Bay County, Kenya. The study found that contrary to fire safety precautionary guidelines, most secondary schools have classrooms with windows fitted with burglary proofs, lack clearly labeled emergency exits and had not fitted emergency alarms. The researcher lamented that this does not conform to Kenya's Ministry of Education safety standards and regulations.

In a similar study, Gichuru (2013) study on 'Fire disaster preparedness strategies in secondary schools in Nyeri central district, Kenya' used descriptive statistic (frequency and percentage) to analyze the responses. The findings revealed that schools are not prepared for fire disaster due to obstructed exits door/escape route, inwardly opening system of classroom doors among others. The situations indicate that there is non-adherence to extant safety regulations (Kihila, 2017). In a study on evaluation of fire safety measures in high-rise buildings in Nigeria Nimlyat, Audu, Ola-Adisa, and Gwatau (2017) advocated that architects and builders should adopt fire safety measures in the design of buildings by careful observance of building codes and standards. Proper installation of systems that are sensitive to fire and fire suppression components should be considered. Nimlyat *et al.* (2017) further recommended that the occupants of buildings should also be well educated on fire safety to prevent fire outbreak or unnecessary spread of fire in case of any outbreak.

Regardless of the laid down safety guidelines and recommendations in Nigeria, studies have shown that there are lack of adequate and effective implementation of disaster management plans and policies at all levels of government (Pathak, 2017). Lack of fire safety plans and other laid down disaster frameworks for the safety of lives and properties of school users were also apprehended. Recently, Ilorin metropolis has experienced a population explosion and different cases of fire incidents which includes secondary schools like Mary International School, Water View Area, Ilorin in 2012. St. James CAC Junior Secondary School, New Yidi Road and Government High School, Adeta in 2013, and Cherubim and Seraphim College, Sabo-Oke, Ilorin in 2015 among others. Specifically, the renewed emphasis on universal basic education for all school-age children and youth contributed to the continual rise of student enrolments and teachers' work force. This has invariably

given rise to erection of new buildings in both old and new secondary schools but it is not clear if safety of the buildings and users against fire disaster is considered.

However, from records secondary schools in Ilorin have the highest records of incidence of school fires in the last two decades with millions of naira loss to the incidents (KSFH, 2017). For example, Bishop Smith Memorial College, Ajase-Ipo Road in 2000, Government Day Secondary School, Tanke, in 2012, Federal Government College, Ogidi Area in 2014, and Cherubim and Seraphim College, Ilorin in 2015 where properties estimated to ₦4m were loss (KSFH, 2017). Preliminary reconnaissance indicates that buildings of many secondary schools particularly classrooms, laboratories, and kitchens among others in Ilorin Metropolis, may not be fire safety-compliance. Without doubt, teachers and learners need appropriately fire protected buildings that are of high utility and value (Nakpodia, 2011), because effective and quality learning requires adequate and safe physical facilities and conducive environment for significant teaching-learning process and outcome (Waudu, 2009 as cited in Gatua, 2015).

Despite the need to ensure protection from fire, available literature points to dearth of this issue in the public space in order to change the narratives of weak fire protection and prevent further loss and damage from unwarranted fire incidents in secondary schools spread across the Metropolis. It is in the light of the foregoing that this study examine the fire safety status of buildings in secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis, Nigeria. The key objectives of the study are to determine classrooms, laboratories, computer/store rooms, and staff rooms' safety and giving recommendation on safety in schools.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study area is Ilorin metropolis. It is located between latitudes 8°20'N and

8°50'0"N of the Equator and longitudes 4°30'0"E and 5°00'0"E of the Greenwich Meridian (see Figure 1). It lies on the southern fringes of savanna region and north of the forest zone of Nigeria. The metropolis is situated in the North central geo-political zone with a land mass of approximately 100 Km² (Adediji, Ajayi and Olawole, 2009; Usman, Malik and Alausa, 2015). It comprises part of three Local Government Areas (LGAs): Ilorin East, Ilorin South, and

Ilorin West (see Fig. 1). Ilorin metropolis is fast growing in population which has necessitated increase in educational institutions from primary to university level. The metropolis has 64 public and 45 registered private senior secondary schools with a population of 47,568 students, 5010 teachers, and 109 principals/head teacher (Ministry of Education and Human Capital Development MOEHCD, 2017).

Figure 1: Kwara State showing Ilorin Metropolis

Source: Olanrewaju and Negedu (2015)

2.2 Research Approach and Data Used

This study adopted descriptive research approach. Data used were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected from senior secondary school II (SSS 2) students and teachers through questionnaire, and participatory observation in form of a checklist. The choice of SS 2 students was because the SS 1 students were new to higher classes and use of laboratories, while the SS 3 students were writing their Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE). Data collected were based on physical assessment of safety status of school buildings

(classroom, laboratory, staffroom, and computer/store room), burglary proof (grill) on doors and windows and their opening system etc. Details of senior secondary schools population were collected from the MOEHCD, records of secondary school fire incidents were obtained from Kwara State Fire Service Headquarters, and review of related literature were secondary data.

2.3 Sample Size

Target population comprises 18 senior public and private secondary schools (PPSSs) sampled from all parts of the three LGA through raffle draws (pick and not

return) from 109 senior PPSSs in the metropolis. The raffle system was done after dividing the schools proportionately: public (64) and private (45) senior secondary schools. The unit of sampling include boarding, day, single sex and coeducation. From experience, the boarding schools are few in number. The tested position of Gay and Airasian (2003) alongside Babbie (2005) that sample size of 10-20% of the population is appropriate for a descriptive survey research was used to justify the sample taken. Meanwhile, at the last stage, the components (administrative and academic) in the 18 schools were stratified into three subcategories; principals, teachers and

students in which the teachers and students subcategories were used.

To target the respondents, a proportionate stratified sampling method according to Stattrek (2018) was used to justify the 143 (14.8%) from the 965 teachers and 557 (14.8%) from the 3765 students population. For respondents' distributions, same method was applied based on each school population. However, where there are few teachers and students the respondents were discreetly increased (refers Table 1). A simple random sampling techniques was employed to select teachers and students respondents that are interested in filling the 700 questionnaire administered.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size of the Sampled Senior Secondary Schools in Ilorin Metropolis

S/N	Schools	Teachers		Students		LGA
		POP	SS	POP	SS	
1	Iqra College, Near pilgrim camp, Ilorin	34	5	73	11	ILW
2	David Akintola College, Sabo Oke, Ilorin.	27	5	26	10	ILE
3	Union Baptist Grammar School, Gaa-Akanbi, Ilorin.	50	7	118	17	ILS
4	Adewumi Abake College, Ilorin	8	5	10	10	ILS
5	Glorious Vision Academy, Ilorin.	24	5	53	10	ILW
6	Ilorin Comprehensive High School.	48	7	114	16	ILW
7	Unilorin Secondary School.	73	10	173	25	ILS
8	Cherubim and Seraphim College, Ilorin.	57	8	300	44	ILE
9	Government Day Secondary School, Adeta.	73	10	336	49	ILW
10	Ilorin Grammar School.	91	12	404	56	ILW
11	Sheik Abdulkadir College, Saw mill, Ilorin.	71	10	278	41	ILW
12	Government Day Secondary School, Odo-Okun, Ilorin.	86	12	394	56	ILW
13	Government High School, Adeta, Ilorin.	62	9	414	56	ILW
14	St. Anthony Senior Secondary School, Ilorin.	67	9	400	56	ILE
15	St. Barnabas Senior Secondary School Ilorin.	31	5	131	19	ILE
16	Bishop Smith Memorial College, Ilorin.	79	11	300	44	ILS
17	Senior Secondary School Danialu.	56	8	181	26	ILS
18	Kwara State Polytechnic Secondary School, Ilorin.	28	5	60	11	ILE
Total		965	143	3765	557	

*Pop = Population; SS = Sample Size; LGA = Local Government Area; ILW = Ilorin West; ILE = Ilorin East; ILS = Ilorin South.

2.4 Instruments Used

Questionnaire and participatory observation in form of a checklist were instruments used to collect data. The questionnaire has nine (9) questions on safety status of classrooms, laboratories, staff common rooms, and computer/store rooms. The opening system and the condition of the doors and windows whether grilled (with burglary proof) or not were also considered. The questionnaire was structured on five options namely: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree with 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 ratings respectively. It was pretested on thirty (30) senior PPSSs teachers and SS 2 students different from those captured in the study using split-half reliability (r_{SB}) for accuracy, simplicity, consistency and understandability. Coefficient value of $r_{SB} = 0.75$ was obtained from the pretest. The researchers' observations in form of a checklist examined safety level of laboratories, classrooms, staff common rooms and computer/storerrooms in terms of numbers of doors and windows, and whether the doors and windows are grilled (with burglary proof) or not.

$$W = \frac{12 \sum (R_i - \bar{R})^2}{m^2 n (n^2 - 1)} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, W = Kendall's coefficient of concordance, R_i = the total rank or rating given to i question by the respondents (j) and is denoted by Equation (2), \bar{R} = the mean value of the total ranks by respondents and is given by Equation (3), m = the total number of respondents, and n = represents the total number of questions.

$$R_i = \sum_{j=1}^m r_i * j \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

And the mean value of the total ranks (\bar{R}) is given in Equation (3) as:

$$\bar{R} = \frac{1}{2} m (n + 1) \dots\dots\dots (3) \quad \text{Ogbonna and Nwaogazie (2015)}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

2.5 Data Analysis

A frequency table was constructed to record the responses for each question. Descriptive statistic (frequency and percentage) was used to analyze the data. To determine whether there is a significant degree of agreement among respondents (students and teachers) on the questionnaire parameters (questions), Kendall's coefficient of concordance was used to measure the agreement among respondents (Enshassi, Mohamed, and Abushaban, 2009; Anyanwu, Akaranta and Nwaogazie, 2016). Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) is a non-parametric statistic, used as a measure of agreement among several (m) judges who are assessing a given set of n objects (Legendre, 2010). Its result (W -statistics) ranges from zero which depicts no agreement to unity which shows complete agreement among the respondents (Abere, Nwaogazie and Akaranta, 2017). Intermediate values of W signify low or high degree of agreement between raters. It was computed by Equation 1–3 (Miroslav and Franc, 2009; Ogbonna and Nwaogazie, 2015).

This section presents results and discusses the findings of the study. From the 700 copies of questionnaire administered, only 645 (92.14%) were suitable for analysis. Responses from questionnaire instrument on

safety status of laboratories, classroom doors, windows among others in fire incident are presented in Table 2. From the results, 51.16% of the respondents disagreed with the researchers' assumption on inspection of schools by fire service corps for fire safety compliance. However, some respondents (39.69%) agreed their classrooms are congested while 45.74% disagreed. Few

among the respondents (37.05%) were of the view that muster point, and hazardous chemicals are not appropriate labeled or have proper signage. Among other questions asked, issues on classrooms' windows having burglary proof (grilled) shows 28.68% of the respondents disagreed, 58.29% agreed and 13.02% did not rent their view on this question.

Table 2: Questionnaire Responses on School Building(s) Safety Level in PPSSs in Ilorin

S/N	Questions	SA	A	N	SD	D
1	Fire-fighting personnel do inspect your school environment at least once in a year for fire safety compliance	114	101	100	176*	154*
2	Your classrooms are congested and have no space that can allow free movement in case of any fire outbreak	120	136	94	120	175
3	Muster point, firefighting equipment, and hazardous chemicals are not appropriate labeled with proper signage	140*	158*	108	126	113
4	Laboratory has two (2) or more doors and the windows are with burglary proof	175*	171*	86	113	100
5	All laboratory chemicals are properly stored	256	209	62	53	65
6	Laboratories have no functional firefighting equipment	198*	182*	84	87	94
7	Classrooms' windows in your school are fortified with burglary proof	181*	195*	84	90	95
8	Classroom, laboratory and escape doors in the school buildings are not outwardly open	174*	170*	100	107	94
9	Students and teachers are aware that there is need to leave the escape routes unobstructed for easy flow of people when the need arises	173	200	92	102	78

*the identified gaps

Source: Authors Field Study, 2021

3.1.2 Observations of School Buildings Doors and Windows

The observation results on safety status of schools buildings viz: laboratory, classroom, staffroom, computer room/store doors and windows are conveyed in Table 3. Looking at Table 3 all the 18 (100%) schools surveyed have laboratories, classroom and staff common rooms while only 16 schools have computer/store room in their schools. In

terms of doors availability, 33.33% schools' laboratories, classrooms (22.22%), staff common rooms (61.11%), and 62.5% schools computer room/store have only one (1) door. There were two (2) doors in 66.67%, 77.78%, 38.89% and 37.5% schools' laboratories, classrooms, staffrooms, and computer rooms respectively. None of the schools has three (3) doors. In terms of windows, all the 18

(100%) schools' laboratories, classrooms (94.44%), staffrooms (88.89%), and 87.5% schools' computer rooms/store have more than three (3) windows each. There were two (2) windows in each of 5.56% schools'

classroom and staffroom, and 6.25% school computer/store room. Meanwhile, 5.56% of the schools surveyed has staffroom and 6.25% have computer/storeroom with only one (1) window (refers Table 3).

Table 3: Observations on Safety Level of Laboratory, Classes, Computer/storeroom and Staffroom Doors and Windows in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin

Facilities	Items						Grilled (Have burglary proof)			
	Door(s)			Window(s)			Door(s)		Window(s)	
	1	2	3	1	2	3	Yes	No	Yes	No
Laboratory	6*	12	-	-	-	18	3	15	13*	5
Classes	4	14	-	-	1	17	-	18	13*	5
Staff room	11*	7	-	1	1	16	2	16	13*	5
Others	10*	6	-	1	1	14	13*	3	14*	2

*Gaps identified

Source: Authors Field Study, 2021

Furthermore, on grilling status of doors and windows, Table 3 shows that doors in 16.67% of the schools' laboratories, staffrooms (11.11%), and computer/store rooms (81.25%) are fastened with burglary proof (grilled). The windows in 72.22% laboratories, classrooms, staffrooms, and 87.5% computer/store rooms of the schools are also fastened with burglary proof (grilled). In spite large number of windows in all and specifically computer/store room doors in most of the schools observed are grilled, yet, doors in 83.33% of the schools' laboratories, classrooms (100%), staffrooms (88.89%), and computer/storeroom (18.75%) are without fixed burglary proofs. Likewise,

27.78% of the schools' laboratories, classrooms, staffrooms, and 12.5% of the schools' computer/storeroom windows are not grilled.

3.1.3 Evaluation of School Building Safety Level through Kendall's (w) Statistic

Table 4 reflects how Kendall's coefficient of concordance (w) for safety level of school buildings against fire incident was calculated from the questionnaire parameters. The result from Kendall's coefficient of concordance (w-statistics) evaluation was 0.454. This indicates a low degree of agreement among respondents.

Table 4: Evaluation of Kendall's (w) Statistic for School Building(s) Safety Level

S/N	M	N	R _i	\bar{R}	$(R_i - \bar{R})^2$
1	645	9	1780	3225	2088025
2	645	9	1841	3225	1915456
3	645	9	2021	3225	1449616
4	645	9	2143	3225	1170724
5	645	9	2473	3225	565504
6	645	9	2238	3225	974169
7	645	9	2212	3225	1026169
8	645	9	2158	3225	1138489
9	645	9	2223	3225	1004004
Total			$\Sigma(R_i - \bar{R})^2 =$		11332156

Kendall's (w) statistics = 0.454

3.2 Discussion

Fire safety preparedness is better when it starts right from the design and construction of school buildings. Fire Service Act, Cap F29, laws of the Federation of Nigeria under National Fire Safety Code 2013 requires that all educational institutions must be inspected by fire service headquarters of the various States prior their establishment and subsequently after establishment annually. Sadly, reverse is the case as regards secondary schools in Ilorin especially in the last one year based on finding in this study. From the results (refer Table 3), the respondents (51.16%) shows high level of disagreement to inspections of schools by Fire Service men for fire safety compliance. Supporting the respondents' views, only a school principal confirmed visitations by a University (Unilorin) fire service corps in the previous one year. Evaluation of physical and environmental preparedness of schools against incident of fire is important therefore, constant school visitations by officers and men of KSFSH should be emphasized. The evaluation will help to examine expired or defected firefighting facilities like corroded portable fire extinguishers (PFEs) from exploding.

Access to basic education requires sufficient and proper facilities such as classrooms being put in place at all times. An investigation into the classroom populations indicates that most school do admits students above their carrying capacities. Per observation, students' population above 50 was seen in 63.64% of public and 45-50 students in 42.86% of private secondary schools classrooms. Though, classrooms in 57.14% of the private secondary schools have between 8-30 students. Considering number of students seen in the classes it can be said that classrooms in PPSSs in Ilorin are overcrowded. No doubt, large number of students in a class is against the National Policy on Education regulation of 35-40 students per class (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). By implication, in the event

of fire incident, crowdedness will increase the risk of human injuries (such as trampling) and fatalities as students scampered to exit the classrooms (Kobes, Helsloot, Vries, and Post, 2010).

Albeit the number of students that exceeded the limits per class, about 50% of the schools have classrooms arrangement that will enable quick and effective movement of extinguishing materials towards the source of the fire, and evacuation of students and teachers from affected classroom. The classroom arrangements probably made almost half of the respondents (45.74%) from Table 2 to be confident that their classrooms are not crowded. However, in some schools, about 40% of respondents insisted that their classrooms are crowded and would not allow free movement of students and teachers when there is fire accident. Students' overpopulation in a class can be solved by erecting more safe buildings and admission of students based on schools' carrying capacities. This has however become the norm in many schools as over crowdedness has been reported by Nakpodia (2011) who observed that most public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria had 50-150 students in a classroom designed for only 40 students. A similarity is in a study in Kenya where 66.67% of the schools investigated had student numbers exceeding the required limit of 40 students per class (Omolo and Simatwa, 2010).

Strategic areas and materials (such as muster point, hazardous chemicals etcetera) should have appropriate labels and signage and respondents (37.05%) from across the schools (Table 2) claimed that the areas are properly labeled. In the same vein, 72.09% of the respondents said the laboratory chemicals are properly stored and labeled. Contrarily, from the observation only fixed portable fire extinguishers and laboratory chemicals were seen arranged and properly stored in few schools (see Plate I). Muster/emergency point and other safety device were generally neither labeled nor having proper signage that will even enable visitors to be aware of fire safety instructions or areas that could

portend risks in the schools. None-labeling of firefighting equipment in schools can put lives of teachers, students and other visitors in danger. Associated chaos during a fire

event include confusion and collision when there is no sense of direction or indicator that will guide the users on their safety.

Plate i: Stored Chemicals in one of the Schools Chemistry Laboratory

Source: Field survey, 2021

It is observed that most schools (66.67%) have laboratories with two (2) doors, and majority (72.22%) of the laboratories windows and a few laboratories doors (16.67%) are grilled with burglary proof (see Plate II). Responses of 58.3% staff and students and the recorded physical observation (of approximately 72.22% of the schools) revealed that classrooms windows are protected with iron bars (for example, see Plate III). From the results 61% of staffrooms and about 63% of computer room can be considered not safe when there is fire because they have only one entry point and more than three (3) windows which are grilled with iron bars. Staffroom doors in 88.89% of the schools are grill free unlike the computer/store room which was barricaded in 77.78% of the schools that have it. Although, some schools have casement and sliding windows in their buildings, a grilled staff common room will pose serious danger

on students' academic records and other records kept in the staff common room(s). It will also threaten lives of teachers particularly the physically challenged and those that are easily panicky.

Primarily, grilling of windows and doors in the schools is a preventive measure against unauthorized access into laboratories and computer rooms thus reducing theft of reagents, other apparatuses, learning aids computer hardware and other valuable equipment kept in the schools. Conversely, this is not appropriate for fire safety because there is high tendency of confusion, collision, and stampeding by students during fire incidents. In a fire outbreak students trapped in a laboratory may suffer suffocation and injuries because of overcrowded rooms. Besides, provision of only one or two door(s) is not fire-safety compliant coupled with windows which could be used as alternative means of escape that have been grilled.

Plate ii: Grilled Laboratory Windows in some of the Schools Surveyed
Source: Field survey, 2021

Plate iii: Classroom Windows with Burglary proofs in some of the Schools
Source: Field survey, 2021

Issues on the opening of doors shows that 53.33% of the respondents agreed the doors in their school buildings are inwardly open (refer Table 2). Inwardly open doors will increase the risk and susceptibility of school users and visitors to fire and its effects, because, to open doors from inside in fire cases will be difficult. As evident there was awareness among respondents (57.83%) to leave escape routes unobstructed for easy flow of people and materials when the needs arise. This agrees with findings of Gichuru (2013) in Kenya that classroom doors in most secondary schools are inwardly opened and escape routes not obstructed. Despite the fact that classrooms and laboratories in many schools have two (2) doors and more than three (3) windows as shown in Table 3, they are not secure for teaching and learning in the event of fire outbreak. It was also observed that some electrical cables and switch boxes of ceiling fans are not insulated in some of the schools. This may lead to sparks during repairs, use or when there is high power voltage.

The Kendall's analysis in Table 4 shows 0.454 (45.4%) level of agreement amongst the respondents on safety status of school buildings which is quite low. This low level of agreement implies that the assumption of classrooms, laboratories, and staffrooms in PPSSs in Ilorin metropolis being safe in the event of fire incident is refuted. No doubt, several factors identified such as grilling of windows, congestion of the classrooms and laboratories, poor identification of muster points, poorly insulated electrical cables are key factors of risks during fire incidents.

4. CONCLUSION

School buildings are essential components in teaching and learning hence they should be safe for users. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that, for many PPSSs in Ilorin metropolis, school buildings cannot be considered as safely protected from fire incidents. This is based on evidential facts from questionnaire

administration and participant observation conducted in 18 secondary schools across the metropolis.

5. RECOMMENDATION

1. Safety codes such as Fire Safety Code of Nigeria, (2013) and National Building Code, (2006) should be effectively implemented and enforced with severe penalty for schools that violate it. In the same direction, periodic assessment of schools by the Kwara State should be emphasized and the report submitted to the Ministry of Education and Human Capital Development.
2. Windows of laboratories, classrooms and staff common rooms should not be grilled and doors should be outwardly open to avoid tramping and stampeding of students and teachers when taking heed for safety in fire disaster situation.
3. Congestion of classrooms and laboratories should be avoided and sitting arrangement should be spacious enough to allow free movement of people and material in fire tragedy.

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